

INTERNET OF THINGS IN INDUSTRIAL LOGISTIC PROCESSES

Author(s)*: Florin LUNGU¹, Mircea TEODORESCU²
Position: Prof., PhD¹, PhD Student²
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Address: Cluj-Napoca, Memorandumului, Str., No. 28, Romania
Email: florin.lungu@mis.utcluj.ro¹, m.teodorescu@yahoo.com²
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro>

Abstract

Purpose - the purpose of this article is to explore how the Internet of Things has influenced and continues to influence manufacturing firms in terms of production and inventory tracking.

Methodology/approach - the objectives of the study are to identify the IoT impact in the production process and prioritize the IT impact in the stages of the production process and optimal stock sizing, using the methodology of comparison between various types of advanced technologies, specific IoT and suitable mining methods to develop an easy information extraction infrastructure. implemented and easy to use, one of the purposes being to track production in real time.

Findings - at the same time, the connection between the IoT and Smart Factory concepts, tracking production and stocks in real time by implementing them is also addressed.

Research limitations/implications -the limitations of the research are that all the information was taken from the literature we studied and not from a practical application of IoT in a company.

Practical implications - at the same time, the connection between the IoT and Smart Factory concepts, tracking production and stocks in real time by implementing them is also addressed.

Originality/value - this article highlights the best solutions for tracking production and stocks using IoT and Smart Factory.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Smart Factory, Decision Tree

GENERAL IoT CONSIDERATIONS

The Internet of Things (IoT) recognized as the superstar of future technology because it is gaining a lot of followers in more and more industries. IoT has brought about a paradigm shift that transforms the way we do business, allowing businesses to create value-added services to improve their sustainability. For example, the ubiquity of wireless sensors extends digital connectivity to tasks, processes and services.

Increased IoT (Lee Inn, 2019) was phenomenal in terms of the volume of sales and the number of companies and individual implementers. The IoT market will reach about \$ 520 billion by 2021, more than double the 2017 level.

In an IoT ecosystem, its components add value. Because typical IoT services require the integration of several devices and software modules often made by different providers, most companies do not have the technical expertise necessary to develop the necessary services. For example, businesses in the area of supply chain management would try to boost IOT platforms to develop services quickly and at low cost.

The IoT ecosystem of a organization consists of a variety of stakeholders, including network providers, software providers, developers, and users. Five primary actors in the IoT ecosystem are established based on field practices studies. Below figure shows the company's five key players of the IoT ecosystem.

An company should be viewed as part of a market community that spans a number of sectors, not as a leader of a particular industry. In addition, with the introduction of IoT, the change to another idea was

illuminated, that of Smart Factory, which incorporates a range of IT solutions, one of the goals being the real-time output monitoring.

Figure 1. Scheme of the 5 key players of the IoT ecosystem (Lee Inn, 2019)

The goal of a Smart Factory is to create value for businesses and customers through IoT services. New IoT platforms are constantly developing and offering new opportunities and challenges for businesses, often being preferred to internal development.

THE “SMART FACTORY” CONCEPT

In recent years, the manufacturing industry has undergone a dramatic change through different parallel developments. Researchers from IFF Sttgarth coordinated studies on the "Smart Factory" (Lucke, Constantinescu and Westkampfer, 2008). Globalization and the desire to produce highly personalized products have led to a greater variety of solutions and shorter product life cycles. Short product planning horizons and product life cycles reduce the size of the batch and therefore require high production flexibility. To make the correct management decisions, real-time information is indispensable.

Dynamic factory changes, caused by internal or external turbulence, such as a car malfunction or fluctuation of market orders, can often not be taken into account and therefore lead to wrong decisions at the planning levels. Thus, a great deal of flexibility is needed in terms of manufacturing resources, their planning and control (Lucke, Constantinescu and Westkampfer, 2008)

The coordination of several heterogeneous subsystems that provide the resources, materials and information used in the workplace is necessary to ensure a constant consumption of resources. To achieve this synchronization, numerous specialized systems and software applications, such as resource management systems, MES or ERP systems are used. Even the slightest difference between real and digital saved data, for example, initiated by a malfunction, leads to planning discrepancies and errors in the optimal workflow.

Smart Factory design and development requires the definition of the concept as a first step. After the development of digital and virtual factories, the next step in the evolution of factories is the fusion of the physical and virtual worlds under a so-called smart factory.

The "Smart Factory" applications have to address the following three issues, which come from many challenges:

1. How is an object identified?
2. Where is an object in the factory?
3. What is the situation or state of an object?

Identification

Identifying items is one of a factory's essential problems, it assigns knowledge regarding the simulated environment as the operation phases of certain real-life artifacts. Thus, in an highly dynamic manufacturing setting, identifying techniques, marks, indicators, sensor readers and contact facilities unique to their mission have to be identified and selected.

Location

To optimize processes and minimize downtime inside the Smart Factory, localization is needed to have clear knowledge of the objects' location. The precision of a positioning device will vary from 0,15m - 1m, depending on the goal. Furthermore, a positioning device used in a manufacturing setting must work systematically and be resilient to environmental factors, electromagnetic fields, dust noise etc.

Status Knowledge

Assistive devices need to know the role or condition of artifacts in a smart factory and give context-aware knowledge and patients. Extremely complex data such as an object's location, should be changed every 10 to 30 seconds.

IOT AND PRODUCTION PROGRAMMING

Recent research in the field of smart enterprises focuses on real-time tracking of production data and the coordination of inventories and production planning according to possible exceptions (errors) that may occur during the production process.

The developments in wireless technologies provide opportunities for intelligent manufacturing, with real-time traceability, visibility and interoperability in production planning, execution and control. However, during the production phase, exceptions often disrupt the operations of a manufacturing system. These studies were completed by a group of Chinese researchers (Zhang, Wang and Wu, 2016).

This is mainly due to the fact that the management team cannot obtain information on the dynamic changes of the execution process in a timely manner and there is no real-time performance analysis and diagnostic service (PAEDM). When an exception occurs, it gradually spreads due to the lack of timely, accurate and consistent manufacturing information and the exceptional diagnostic model, which further aggravates the production process. Therefore, it is essential for companies to improve their production management mode with advanced technologies and models to improve quality and efficiency. By extending IoT technologies, such as RFID and barcode to the production environment, real-time and multi-source manufacturing data has become ubiquitous.

In general, when a manufacturing process is monitored in real time, the data obtained can be mined and appropriate information can be discovered so that production performance analysis can be performed. In doing so, the performance of a manufacturing process can be continuously improved. Petri nets (PN) are known to be powerful for process modeling (graphical or mathematical) and formal verification. Thus, they are widely adopted for modeling, analyzing and controlling discrete event systems. Tree Decision is a supervised data extraction technique and can serve as an effective tool for multivariate data analysis. It is a discovery-based approach based on data from rich sources, to be used in knowledge discovery and decision support analysis.

As an attempt to combine IoT, PN, and DT technologies for real-time data analysis, an IoT-compatible performance and error diagnosis (PAEDM) model can be developed. The purpose is to answer the following two important questions:

- 1) how to model the dynamics of the system using HTCPN so that production performance analysis can be done in real time?
- 2) how to dynamically provide information of qualitative and quantitative exceptions, so that the analysis is persuasive and objective?

Applying Internet of Things to manufacturing lines

Using RFID devices, wireless networks, and mobile sensors, the IoT is recognized to be crucial in many industrial applications. Thus, IoT, is becoming more and more attractive both from an industrial and academic point of view.

For example, to address production planning, a real-time RFID enabled execution system is presented. This is achieved by systematically implementing RFID devices in the "shop-floor" to track manufacturing objects and collect real-time production data.

By using IoT, the dynamic problem of synchronized logistics production (PLS) for a manufacturer is investigated. Cloud and IoT infrastructures are systematically integrated to enable an intelligent PLS control mechanism with dynamic multi-level adaptability.

Petri nets (PNS)

Nowadays, Petri Nets have been successfully used for modeling, controlling, and analyzing discrete systems and are characterized by competition, parallelism, asynchrony, interlocking, conflict and event-driven processes. PNS is defined as a bipartite graph. directed with two types of nodes called places and transitions. The status is described as "tokens" also called bookmarks or tokens. During execution, the number of bookmarks and their distribution reflects the change of the state of the object being tracked. In the graphic representation, the places are drawn as circles, the transitions in the form of rectangles or bars, the marks are represented by black dots and the arcs by arrows.

For modeling dynamic behavior, a colored Petri Nets System with intelligent marking (token) is proposed for modeling and controlling reconfigurable manufacturing systems. In the model, the markings presenting the places (P) have real-time information about the state of the system through a system identical to the smart cards. Given this advantage, the dynamic changes of the system can be easily interpreted. A method for optimal control of Petri nets can be proposed. Thus the legal markings are classified into several subsets

Also developed a new modeling method based on Petri Colored Networks based on RFID sensors where colored markings are used to describe the dynamic evolution of the state of the products in real time. A new colorful PN model can be proposed for real-time programming of chip-based multi-processor platforms.

Decision trees

DT is one of the most popular machine learning techniques due to the ability and ease with which immediate production decisions can be made. This can be used to explore the relationships between a large number of input attributes and output targets. There are three main phases of rules in DT learning.

Phase1: create a tree rule as large as possible from a set of inputs based on attribute measurement;

Phase 2: cutting the branches that have little statistical validity in the tree type rule;

Phase 3: processing the data from the cut tree to improve its understanding.

Over the years, a series of classification algorithms have been proposed for DT input values, such as ID3, Fuzzy-ID3, C4.5, EC4.5 and CART. Among them, C4.5 deserves special attention for its advantages, offering good classification accuracy. Similarly, Fuzzy-ID3 also proved to be powerful for the ability to generate a decipherable fuzzy decision tree by using fuzzy sets.

For analyzing exceptions on the production line, DT is one of the most comprehensive methods. With data provided by RFID from the production line, a mined (data extraction) approach (DT-based model) was proposed to estimate the standard operating time.

IMPLEMENTATION ON THE PRODUCTION LINE

To be well-operated, a manufacturing company should achieve real-time, seamless connectivity and interoperability between physical manufacturing systems and enterprise information systems (EIS).

It is imperative to find the most appropriate form of transmission of information from the production line to the basic application, which controls the production scheduling of the entire production line but the volume of information would be huge, which is why it is filtered through a model described below.

To do this, real-time performance analysis and exception diagnostics (PEDM) aims to apply advanced Internet of Things technologies and data mining methods to develop an easy-to-implement and easy-to-deploy information extraction infrastructure. to be used. The overall architecture of the proposed integrated model is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of three modules, namely the intelligent storage module activated for IoT, the module for analyzing the performance in real time and of the production based on events and PN and the third module: DT. - how to extract the exception and diagnose the causes. These are explained below.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the Real Time Production Planning Tracking Model (Zhang, Wang and Wu, 2016).

Smart store-floor smart store module IoT

The objective of this module is to build an intelligent production line based on IoT technologies. It aims to create a link for the communication of information between physical manufacturing systems and the process of information multiplication. IoT technologies (RFID, or Wireless Networks) are configured to form a physical manufacturing system based on the required information. Based on the configuration, a manufacturing environment with low cost and reliable sensors is built.

How to analyze the real-time performance of production based on critical events and CPN

This module is responsible for modeling the dynamic behavior of a manufacturing system and processing the insignificant data captured by sensors for critical production events. As shown in the middle of Figure 2, the multilevel event model and HTCPN technology (“Hierarchical Timed Colored Petri Net”) are combined to analyze the production performance in real time.

HTCPNs are built on the multilevel event model. In Petri Nets, places are used to represent the state of resources in the system; Transition to represent activities and macro transitions are used for subsystem modeling; I/O functions to represent the relationship between transitions and places; adding time delays to I/O transitions and functions; colored markers to represent a certain type of product. This system in which IoT is implemented can be updated according to the information on the manufacturing line in real time. As a result, information on production performance, such as production progress, quality distribution, etc. can be accessed.

Decision Tree(DT)- Based Exception Extraction and Cause Diagnosis Module

An exception-event defines an abnormal state of an object or system. This occurs, for example, in a manufacturing stage and disrupts the normal or planned production plan, for example, an exception occurs when production progresses with a slight deviation from the plan. Exception diagnostics aims to detect exceptions and find the causes once they occur. It provides important information in order to avoid system errors, which lead to maintaining the efficiency of the production.

The working logic of this module is presented at the top of Figure 2. First of all, the DTs for extracting the exceptions and diagnosing the causes are constructed taking into account the conditions of the process. Algorithm C4.5 is used in the construction of the DT for the exception extraction. Because there is a lot of vague and uncertain information during data collection, the interactive Fuzzy Dichotomizer 3 algorithm is used to diagnose causes. Then, when information on production performance is obtained, the extraction of DT exceptions is accessed according to the process. As a result, the production conditions are analyzed based on these rules. Finally, if an exception is detected, the DT diagnosis of the exceptions is applied.

Production performance analysis

Once the model is built, and the tokens and their colors are set to be associated with real-time resources, the performance of the production line can be analyzed as follows:

- 1) The intermediate marking for the inventory and the state of the raw materials under processing is monitored in real time.
- 2) Add additional places for each transition in order to record the frequency of their changes as well as their result so that the maximum technological loading of the machines can be achieved.
- 3) The performance analysis is performed to measure the time required for the parts to wait in line for production, the size of the waiting times, the production cycle time and so on.

With these measurements, the simulation is done to obtain production performance and to transmit the report to the basic application. In doing so, we extract key information for decision making, which is much better than transferring a large volume of events to your attention.

IOT AND STOCK TRACKING

The optimization of information on deposits plays a decisive role in managing the supply chain with goods and only through a simple procedure of acquisition, inventory control and shipment in warehouse management, we can efficiently reduce the cost of the enterprise and improve the quality and competitiveness of the services. With the development of the warehouse management technology, stock records are functioning faster and faster, at the same time, warehouse operations and management control have become more and more complicated. It is difficult for manual operations to process a huge amount of data due to the low efficiency and time consuming, even more, there will be huge losses if there are errors. Therefore, the use of intelligent warehouse management tools has become an urgent need for today's businesses. One of the simplest methods has as technical basis the reading of the labels with the help of the hand readers (Ding, 2013).

The intelligent warehouse management program based on Internet of Things, in terms of hardware, consists of electronic labels, bar code readers and fixed readers; from the software point of view, it consists of: - a management system and electronic labels on the shelf. The overall structure of the system is shown in

The portable tag barcode reader represents recording equipment in operation in / from storage in the warehouse management system and is also the basic equipment of the entire system. Staff use the handheld reader to scan the goods barcode, then write the storage information on the RFID tags to complete the goods inventory.

However, this method involves quite frequent operator interventions, which is why human errors can occur. Other methods have been developed to take this into account, one of them being the WSN - a wireless sensor network, that is, a network of wireless sensors that can identify at any time the position of a pallet with cargo on the shelf and its contents, as well. to make it easy to keep track of the number of pieces in each product.

Fig. 3. General structure of hand-reader based systems (Ding, 2013)

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) (Falkenberg, R, s.a. 2017) have been a major research topic in recent years, a method that covers a diverse area of research, for example routing algorithms, energy harvesting, management, security and confidentiality. According to this versatile range of works, wide variations of WSN tests have been developed. In addition, there are federations of WSNs that combine multiple installations into a single widespread platform. Some of the most popular platforms are (Falkenberg, R, s.a. 2017):

- a) MoteLab - wireless network developed by Harvard and published in 2005. It was one of the first fully developed WSNs. MoteLab is an open source tool that is accessible on the Internet. Its web access facilitates remote programming and user programming.
- b) Future Internet of Things: FIT/IoT-Lab - is a large-scale erogenous research facility, with a federation of over 6 locations and over 2000 nodes in total. In order to interact with the nodes, it has command line interfaces through the user's virtual machines.
- c) Indriya - is a low cost WSN 3D testing platform implemented at the National University of Singapore. The 127 wireless nodes are connected with active USB cables. This USB infrastructure provides a back channel for remote programming and powering of sensor nodes.
- d) WISEBED - is a IoT research facility with a heterogeneous implementation in which each partner maintains its own testbed. There is also an overlay network that provides access to all test bases as a single large IoT implementation for analysis.

A possible alternative may be the one provided by **PhyNet lab** as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. PhyNet containers (Falkenberg, R, 2017)

It is located in a large warehouse, providing space for a considerable amount of containers. Each container carries a PhyNode module on the front, which allows the communication with the infrastructure. The modules function as internet access points and are equally distributed in the warehouse. A brief description of PhyNetLab and its components is presented below (Falkenberg, R, s.a. 2017).

Hardware

PhyNode (see figure below) consists of two parts, a main network board for management and the actual experiment platform, which is a "swappable" (SSB) board.

Figure 5. PhyNode hardware (Falkenberg, R, 2017)

The management platform is based on the backbone of the ZigBee network and can be used, for example, to update the firmware of the board. The SSB heart is a FRAM (ferroelectric) memory. Compared to conventional RAM, the 64 kB FRAM is very durable in terms of memory access and energy efficient. Radio Communication is achieved with low Power Consumption Sub - 1 GHz Transmission for Short Range Devices (SRD). In addition, the board includes sensors that capture accelerations, temperature, color, infrared rays and ambient light. Interaction is possible using buttons and a small LCD. The SSB can be programmed to be energy neutral. It is designed to allow switching to an alternate power source if energy storage is exhausted.

Software

To enable rapid development of applications in low energy systems, we have developed an IoT in Kratos operating system. It supports developers with a complete set of libraries and C ++ functions, which can be "tailored" to suit the needs of a distinct application and thus save resources by implementing the necessary system components.

Kratos was developed primarily with PhyNetLab and therefore offers full support in the PhyNode platform. Furthermore, PhyNetLab and Kratos allow mutual research on hardware and software design for various low-energy IoT deployments. By doing so, PhyNetLab provides us with information on how to design power and network software components for an operating system as we have difficult to manage resources. In the other direction, software requirements for enabling maintenance and deploying applications for PhyNetLab have influenced the choice of hardware components used in PhyNode.

This working method allows the efficient management of a raw material warehouse by the method described above on the PhyNetLab platform, a platform that is in the process of being developed through the Kratos operating system.

Such a network created leads to real-time tracking of stock management based on the above research.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of the "Smart Factory" based on the new IoT technologies allows to obtain in real time the information necessary for the production management. The monitoring and planning of the production in real time by the methods described in the present report, as well as the management of the stocks provide extremely relevant information to the management team and come in its aid in maintaining the competitiveness of the economic operator under current market conditions.

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